

I'M VACCINATED

WHEN DO I NEED TO TEST FOR COVID-19?

Although the risk that fully vaccinated people could become severely ill and die of COVID-19 is low, any fully vaccinated person who encounters the following circumstances should get tested.

When exposed to a person with COVID-19 and symptoms develop

WHEN TO
GET
TESTED

When living or working in a congregate setting and exposed to a person with COVID-19, even if asymptomatic

When COVID-19 symptoms develop regardless of known exposure

When returning to the US from international travel

As required by employer guidelines and policies